

ORGANIZATIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OF BUSINESS ENTITIES

Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich –

Base doctoral student of Tashkent State University of Economics

Bayisbayevjavlon@gmail.com

+998 97 542 49 47

Annotation. This article analyzed scientific-theoretical approaches to the concepts of social responsibility of business entities, social responsibility, opinions, ideas of scientists, basic principles of Social Responsibility, economic essence, social entrepreneurship. Recommendations and proposals have been cited to increase the social responsibility of entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Social Responsibility, Community, subject, society, organization, profit, income, needy persons, socially vulnerable layer, youth, people, innovation.

Introduction

The social responsibility of business entities arose as a socio-economic phenomenon, as a public response to existing social problems. The main purpose of the social responsibility of business entities is to benefit society, such a business entity prioritizes the interests of society in its activities.

It is noted that the social responsibility of business entities is the activity of legal entities and individual entrepreneurs aimed at alleviating or solving certain social problems of the population and their consequences. The purpose of social responsibility of business entities is to improve the standard of living of the socially vulnerable.

Social entrepreneurship is one of the factors that stimulate the fight against unemployment, as well as the production of goods and services.

Social entrepreneurship - in the activities of individuals, groups, start-up companies or entrepreneurs, they are engaged in the development, financing and

implementation of solutions to social, cultural or environmental problems. This concept can be applied to a variety of organizations that differ in size, purpose, and beliefs. For-profit entrepreneurs usually measure their performance using business metrics such as profits, revenues, shares and their prices.

It can be cited as another evidence that social entrepreneurship is one of the factors that stimulate the fight against unemployment, as well as the production of goods and the provision of services.

The social responsibility of business entities mainly consists in improving the standard of living of the socially vulnerable layer of the company's employees, providing them with work, providing benefits and providing services in the production of social goods. Social responsibility of business entities is mainly socially unstable or disabled persons are involved in the work of the enterprise.

The first group of authors focuses on the main definition of an entrepreneur. J.G. Dees says that corporate social responsibility is the result and creation of a particularly creative and innovative leader. As a result, products suitable for the new social environment are created [2].

David Bornstein, the social responsibility of business entities uses many creative, non-traditional strategies, due to which he even replaced the term "social innovator" with the term "social responsibility of the entrepreneur". [3].

John Elkington and Pamela Hartigan, in their book *The Power of Idiots*, find that corporate social responsibility is not as far-fetched a concept as many have made it out to be. They argue that these men and women benefit from social production where others do not expect to benefit. They also ignore evidence that their businesses are failing and end up measuring results they are not equipped to measure [4].

Regardless of the sector of society, some organizations (i.e. corporations or unincorporated associations, societies, associations or) cooperatives, act without taking into account the social responsibility of business entities. The lack of social responsibility of business entities can have a great impact on society.

The social responsibility of entrepreneurs can include the types of careers and professional information, and does not fail to contribute to social work and community development. Therefore, entrepreneurs are not able to quickly identify socially responsible. In order to understand more clearly what the social responsibility of entrepreneurs means, it is necessary to separate the functions of social responsibility from other voluntary sector and philanthropic activities and to define the boundaries within which social responsibility operates.

Gaining a broader understanding of how an issue relates to society allows entrepreneurs to develop innovative solutions to corporate social responsibility and mobilize available resources to impact a larger global community.

Bill Drayton founded Ashoka in 1980, an organization that supports local entrepreneurs to be socially responsible. Drayton tells his employees to look for four qualities: creativity, entrepreneurial quality, social impact of the idea, and ethical fiber [9].

Entrepreneurial quality is formed from creativity. Entrepreneurs should not only have an idea of what to do, but also know how to do it and show real results in doing it. The social responsibility of entrepreneurs is manifested by the company's belief in development in the future and actions to implement it, by clearly envisioning it. This transformation process is described as creating imbalances in the market by converting antagonistic assets into complementary ones. [7].

The idea of social impact posits that change can be made after the original founder is gone. If an idea has intrinsic social value, after its implementation it will lead to change even without the charismatic leadership of the first entrepreneur. Most entrepreneurs have not learned the skills necessary to make their ideas a reality. Instead, they bring in a team of skilled people around them. It is this idea that attracts this team.

One of the distinguishing features of socially responsible entrepreneurship is that they rarely take credit for making a difference. They emphasize that the change

they bring depends on those around them, and also tend to be emotional; they try to combat suffering, not profit first.

The lack of willing investors leads to a second problem in social entrepreneurship: the pay gap. Corporate Social Responsibility Social entrepreneurs and their workers are often given reduced or non-existent wages, especially when businesses start up. As such, their businesses struggle to retain skilled, loyal workers. While socially responsible entrepreneurs are addressing some of the world's most pressing issues, they have a hard time confronting the skepticism and mistrust of the communities they seek to serve.

Another reason why socially responsible entrepreneurs often fail is because they help their less fortunate employees. Capitalism is based on the exchange of capital (money) for goods and services. However, social entrepreneurs employ new business models that do not rely on the standard exchange of capital to make their organizations sustainable. This self-sustainability distinguishes social businesses from charities, which rely almost entirely on donations and external funding.

Conclusions and suggestions

An entrepreneur serves to improve socio-economic life with his own initiative and funds, responsibility for his activities creates a business environment in the society, he forms a feeling of serving the interests of the people, his appetite for newness and innovation should correspond to the nature and dynamics of the reforms implemented in our country.

We believe that it is appropriate to implement the following in order to increase the social responsibility of entrepreneurship:

- conducting independent economic activity according to market demand;
- to have responsibility for profit;
- ability to take on economic responsibility and obligation and work at risk;
- striving for innovation;
- compliance with established laws;
- keeping a business secret;

- with a sense of responsibility, that is, to consider ensuring the well-being of one's community and people as the main direction of one's activity.

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